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Research Article

**PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF KETOCONAZOLE
MICROSPONGE TO IMPROVE THERAPEUTICS
EFFECTIVENESS****Sakshi Yadav¹, Ankita Shukla¹, Naveen Gupta¹**
¹Madhyanchal Professional University, Bhopal, M.P.**Abstract:**

Microsponges are porous cross-linked polymers, which have the ability to load a wide range of pharmaceutical active ingredients. They are used topically for long-term treatment applications in addition to the oral route of administration. They are characterized by the efficient distribution of active ingredients, which are loaded at a low quantity to release the drug over longer periods of time by altering the release characteristics. The objective of this study was to develop a novel drug-delivery system that included ketoconazole microsponges. For Eudragit based microsponges, the mean particle size was found to increase with the decrease in the polymer amount. The microsponges showed homogenous particle size distribution with three blade centrifugal stirrer. Stirring speed and time has profound effect on particle size and size distribution of microsponges. The increase in the stirring rate resulted in a reduction in mean particle size. The results of loading efficiency showed that the higher drug loading efficiencies were obtained at the higher drug: polymer ratios. The relatively high production yield and loading efficiency of ethanol entrapped styrene microsponges and Eudragit RS100 microsponges indicated that both the methods are suitable for preparing the microsp sponge formulations. The result concluded that KM2 formulation was best of microsponges because of having maximum polymer concentration of Eudragit RS 100 for retarding release of drug in controlled diffusion kinetics.

Keywords: Ketoconazole, Microsponges, Eudragit RS 100, Quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method, controlled diffusion kinetics

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INTRODUCTION:

The skin is a large multilayered organ which, in an average adult, weighs about eight pounds, exclusive of the fat. It covers a surface exceeding 20,000 square centimeters. It serves as a barrier against physical and chemical attack, regulates body temperature, prevents the invasion of microorganisms, protects against UV rays, and plays a role in the regulation of blood pressure [1]. Thick hairless skin forms frictional surfaces for manipulation and locomotion, and requires extra strength for this purpose. It also possesses numerous sweat glands for cooling during sustained activity, and dense clusters of sensitive sensory endings with a high degree of spatial discrimination, unimpeded by the presence of hairs. Thin hairy skin is responsible for the general cutaneous function over the remainder of the body. Human skin regulates heat and water loss from the body [2]. At the same time it prevents entry of noxious chemicals and microorganisms into the body. In transdermal drug delivery, the membrane can be regarded as a simple physical barrier. More complexity can be introduced by viewing skin as various barriers in a series. We can then introduce barriers in parallel by considering drug transport through pores in the tissue. Degrees of complexity also exist when examining basic structures and functions of the membrane. The drug permeates into or through the skin via three portals of entry: via the follicular region; through the sweat ducts or through the unbroken stratum corneum between these appendages by passive diffusion. Two mechanisms of drug permeation are involved; transepidermal absorption or transfollicular or shunt pathway absorption. Transepidermal absorption involves passage of drug through the epidermis itself and transfollicular absorption involves diffusion of drug through hair follicles and eccrine glands. However, the principle pathway responsible for drug permeation is believed to be transepidermal [3]. Transepidermal permeation first involves partitioning of the drug into the stratum corneum followed by diffusion across the tissue. Most substances diffuse across the stratum corneum via the intercellular lipoidal route. But this route has the disadvantages of limited fractional volume and even more limited productive fractional area in the plane of diffusion. Microsponge delivery systems are uniform, spherical, porous polymeric microspheres having myriad of interconnected voids of particle size range 5- 300µm. These microsponges have the capacity to entrap a wide range of active ingredients such as emollients, fragrances, essential oils, sunscreens and anti-infective, etc. and then release them onto skin over a time and in response to trigger (Sergio Nacht., 1992). Micropores within the spheres comprise a total pore

density of approximately 1mL/g, and pore length 10 ft for extensive drug retention. Further, these porous microspheres with active ingredients can be incorporated in to formulations such as creams, lotions and powders [4]. Microsponges consisting of non-collapsible structures with porous surface through which active ingredients are released in a controlled manner. When applied to the skin, the MDS releases its active ingredient on a time mode and also in response to other stimuli (rubbing, temperature, pH, etc. When compared to conventional formulations, micro sponge system can prevent excessive accumulation of ingredients within the epidermis and the dermis [5]. Potentially, the Microsponge system can reduce significantly the irritation of drugs without reducing their efficacy. Microsponge delivery systems are used to enhance the safety, effectiveness and aesthetic quality of topical prescription, over-the-counter and personal care products. Microsponges are designed to deliver a pharmaceutical active ingredient efficiently at the minimum dose and also to enhance stability, reduce side effects and modify drug release [6]. Ketoconazole is widely recommended orally for the treatment of various fungal infections. One of the major disadvantages of oral therapy in the treatment of skin infections like Seborrhoeic dermatitis and Psoriasis is rapid relapse on the cessation of therapy and the risk of hepatotoxicity [7]. The present work is proposed to design and evaluate microsponge delivery system to recover the therapeutic effectiveness of the topically useful drug ketoconazole. The Microsponge polymeric system are tiny sponge like (Porous) spherical particles are able to entrap active ingredients and then release them onto the skin over a time in response to a activate. They can also extend the product stability because of their unique configuration and improve its aesthetic properties. Microsponges also increase the rate of solubilization of poorly water-soluble drugs by entrapping such drugs in microscopic pores of the microsponges. Because these pores are very small, the drug is in effect reduced to microscopic particles and thus significantly increasing surface area and the rate of solubilization

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Analytical study: The stock solutions (100µg/mL) of the drugs were prepared in phosphate buffer PBS pH 7.4 (Ketoconazole). The stock solutions were appropriately diluted with the respective solvents to obtain a concentration of 20µg /mL. The UV spectrum was recorded in the range of 200-400 nm on Shimadzu 1700 UV spectrophotometer to find the λ max. Construction of calibration curve for drugs was prepared from the stock solution, solutions containing

2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 µg/mL of the drugs were prepared by appropriate dilutions. Absorbance of these solutions was measured at 260 nm for Ketoconazole against respective blank solvents [8].

Preformulation Studies: Preformulation testing is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms of a drug. It can be defined as an investigation of physical and chemical properties of drug substance, alone and when combined with excipients. Hence, a preformulation study on the procured sample of drug includes conducting physical tests and compatibility studies. The parameters included i.e. organoleptic properties, melting point determination, solubility analysis, particle size, flow properties, partition coefficient and IR Spectroscopy for drug-excipient compatibility studies [9].

Preparation of Ketoconazole microsponges: The ketoconazole microsponges were prepared by quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method (Atmaram et. al., 2015; Osmani et. al., 2015). To prepare the inner phase, Eudragit RS 100 was dissolved in 3 mL of methanol and triethylcitrate (TEC) was added at an amount of 20% of the polymer in order to facilitate the plasticity. The drug was then added to the solution and dissolved under ultrasonication at 35°C. The inner phase was poured into the PVA (72000) solution in 200 mL of water (outer phase). The resultant mixture was stirred for 60 min, and filtered through the filter paper (Whatmann filter paper 0.45µm), washed with distilled water and dried at 40°C for 24h. [10-11] The design and composition of various microsponges is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Microsponge formulations using Eudragit RS100

Formulation Code	KM1	KM2	KM3	KM4	KM5	KM6	KM7
Inner phase							
Ketoconazole	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Eudragit RS 100 (g)	2.5	0.83	0.5	0.36	0.28	0.23	0.19
Methanol (mL)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Outer phase							
Distilled water (mL)	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
PVA 72000 (mg)	50	50	50	50	50	50	50

Characterization of Ketoconazole microsponges:

Drug Loading and Drug Entrapment: A sample of ketoconazole microsponges (100mg) was taken for evaluation. The drug loaded microsponges were powdered and dissolved in 10 Oml of phosphate buffer solution, pH 7.4. This solution was filtered after 24 h and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 260 nm against blank solution. The amount of drug loaded and entrapped in the microsponges was calculated.

Particle Size Evaluation: Average particle size of ketoconazole loaded microsponges was determined by an optical microscope using calibrated eye piece and stage micrometer under regular polarized light. A minute quantity of microsponges was spread on a clean glass slide and the average particle size was calculated by measuring 300 particles of each batch. The values were given for the formulations in the form of mean particle size [12].

In-vitro Dissolution Studies: The release of ketoconazole from microsponge was investigated in

phosphate buffer solution, pH 7.4 as a dissolution medium (500ml) using USP type II apparatus. A sample of microsponge equivalent to 100 mg of ketoconazole in a capsule was taken in the basket. A speed of 50 rpm and temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C was maintained throughout the experiment. At fixed intervals, aliquots (5ml) were withdrawn and replaced with fresh dissolution media. The concentration of drug released at different time intervals was then determined by measuring the absorbance using UV spectrophotometer at 260 nm against blank. The dissolution studies were performed in triplicate. The dissolution data was subjected to various release models namely, Zero, First, Higuchi and Peppas [13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical study: The UV spectrum of Ketoconazole in phosphate buffer PBS pH 7.4 was scanned and λ_{max} was found to be 260 nm.

Preformulation Study: The characterization of Ketoconazole pure drug was identified i.e.

description white to off-white in color, crystalline powder and melting point was 148-152°C. The solubility of drug powder was Freely soluble in dichloromethane; soluble in chloroform and in methanol; sparingly soluble in ethanol (95%); practically insoluble in water and in ether. The FT-IR spectrum of the procured ketoconazole (**Figure 2**) was recorded and spectral interpretation was done. The characteristic IR absorption peaks of ketoconazole (**Table 2**) were there in the drug sample spectrum; thus confirming its purity.

Physical Characterization of Microsponges:

Ketoconazole microsponges were prepared by quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method. The method was simple, reproducible and rapid. The product observed to be of pale white colour with good flow properties than as compared with pure drug.

The percentage yield: The percentage yield of different formulations of Ketoconazole microsponges were between 78.34 to 96.117 %. In case of Eudragit RS 100 microsponges, it was revealed that, by increasing drug: polymer ratio there is increase in the production yield of the microsponges (Table 3).

The Percentage drug loading: The percentage entrapment efficiency were also determined for formulations and given in Table 3. The drug loading efficiencies of Ketoconazole microsponges were 84.11 to 97.19 %. In case of Eudragit RS 100 microsponges, it was found that as drug: polymer ratio increases, drug loading efficiency also increases, whereas in case of Salicylic acid microsponges, it was found that, there was no significant effect of concentration of divinylbenzene on production yield and drug loading efficiency.

Particle Size Analysis: Average particle size of microspunge formulations was determined by optical microscopy by using stage micrometer and eye piece micrometer and the values are shown in Table 3. Free-flowing powders with fine Eudragit based microsponges (Ketoconazole) are shown and the mean particle size of Ketoconazole was found to be 87.39 μm - 120.17 μm .

In-vitro Release Studies of Ketoconazole Microsponges: The dissolution of ketoconazole from microsponges was conducted in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 for 8 h. The release profile was estimated by UV spectrum of Ketoconazole in phosphate buffer PBS pH 7.4 at λ_{max} 260 nm. The profiles showed a gradual release of the drug from all the formulations. Cumulative release for the microsponges after 2 h ranged from more than 50 %. Drug release from the

formulations decreased with increase in the amount of polymer in the microsponges. Drug release from Ketoconazole microspunge upto 6 h was found to range from 67.32 % to 76.25 % from all the formulations an the drug release kinetic study followed the diffusion kinetics through the polymer matrices or wall of microsponges. The result confirmed that KM2 formulation was best of microspones because of having maximum polymer concentration of Eudragit RS 100 for retarding release of drug in conteolled diffusion kinetics (Figure 3).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion is now a days the preferred method to prepare porous microparticles. Eudragit RS100 microsponges containing Ketoconazole were successfully prepared by this method as these drugs were found incompatible with reaction conditions of liquid-liquid suspension polymerization. Thus, Microsponges are porous, polymeric microspheres that are typically utilised for topical. delivery over a lengthy period of time. Microsponges are used to deliver a pharmaceutically. active substance at a low dose while simultaneously improving stability, reducing adverse. effects, and changing drug release patterns. The microspunge drug delivery system offers entrapment of its ingredients and is believed to contribute toward reduced side effects, improved stability, increased elegance, and enhanced formulation flexibility.

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Figure 1: Calibration curve of Ketoconazole

Figure 2: FTIR Spectra of Ketoconazole

Table 2: FTIR Spectrum interpretation of Ketoconazole

Functional group	Wave number observed (cm -1)
C=O (carbonyl group)	1646.77
C-O (aliphatic ether group)	1031.84
C-O (cyclic ether)	1244.31

Table 3: Characterizations of different formulations of Ketoconazole

Formulation code	Production yield (%)	Drug Loading efficiency (%)	Particle size (μm)
KM1	78.34 \pm 2.13	84.11 \pm 1.32	87.39 \pm 1.13
KM2	80.23 \pm 1.17	86.45 \pm 0.69	101.21 \pm 1.17
KM3	82.21 \pm 1.23	88.49 \pm 2.01	112.51 \pm 1.13
KM4	85.12 \pm 2.01	90.86 \pm 0.27	105.12 \pm 1.01
KM5	87.25 \pm 1.14	92.38 \pm 1.26	117.25 \pm 1.14
KM6	89.14 \pm 1.90	94.21 \pm 0.39	109.14 \pm 1.20
KM7	96.11 \pm 2.16	97.19 \pm 0.16	120.17 \pm 1.16

Figure 3: Zero-order kinetic plot of Ketoconazole Microsponges